

NOTES

Fig. 1. α -Picolyaminium oxotetrachloro molybdate(V), α -pic.H₄[MoOCl₄] in 12MHCl.

Fig. 2. α -Picolyaminium oxopenta bromomolybdate(V), α -pic.H₄[MoOBr₅] in 48% HBr.

spectrophotometer using AnalaR grade solvents. Electronic spectra of the chloro and bromo salts were taken in 12 M HCl and 48% HBr respectively. Results are tabulated in Table 1. The assignments are made on the basis of previous observations¹⁻³. The diagrammatic representation of the results are given in Figs. 1 and 2.

References

1. H. K. SAHA and M. C. HALDAR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 3097.
2. H. K. SAHA and A. K. BANERJEE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 1861.
3. H. K. SAHA and T. K. RAY CHAUDHURI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 698.
4. H. K. SAHA, R. K. PRAMANIK and B. K. SIKDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 90.

Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes with Tridentate ONO Donor Schiff Bases Derived from Benzoylhydrazide and Salicylaldehyde or Substituted Salicylaldehydes

A. SYAMAL* and B. K. GUPTA

Department of Applied Sciences and Humanities, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119, Haryana and Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Kurukshetra-132 119, Haryana

Manuscript received 15 December 1980, revised 1 June 1981, accepted 15 July 1981

ALTHOUGH there has been considerable interest in the Schiff base complexes of first transition series metal ions^{1,2} little work has been reported on such complexes with higher transition series metal ions. As relatively few dioxouranium(VI) complexes with tridentate Schiff bases are known³, we report here the syntheses of dioxouranium(VI) complexes of the Schiff bases (I).

R=H, 5-Bromo, 5-Chloro, 5-Nitro, 5-Methoxy, 3-Methoxy, 3-Ethoxy, 3,5-Dichloro, 5,6-Benzo.

Experimental

Benzoylhydrazide was prepared according to published procedure⁴. The Schiff bases were prepared by following the method described elsewhere⁵.

General method of syntheses of the complexes: Uranylacetate dihydrate (0.84 g, 2 m mole) was dissolved in 10 ml of methanol. A methanolic solution of the Schiff base (2 m mole in 15 ml) was added to this and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. The precipitate was filtered, washed with methanol and dried *in vacuo*. Yield=70%. U% and N% were determined by standard methods^{5,6}. Molecular weight, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, ir and electronic spectral data were recorded as usual⁷.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLECULAR WEIGHT, CONDUCTANCE AND INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF DIOXOURANIUM(VI) COMPLEXES^a

Complex/ Stoichiometry	M. W. Found (Calcd.)	%U Found (Calcd.)	%N Found (Calcd.)	ΔM $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{OUO})$ cm^{-1}	f_{UO} $\text{m dynes}/\text{\AA}$	R_{UO} \AA	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{OUO})\text{cm}^{-1}$
$\text{UO}_2(\text{sal-BZH})\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	551 (540)	43.42 (44.07)	4.95 (5.18)	8	910	6.88	1.74	830
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{U}$								
$\text{UO}_2(5\text{-bromosal-BZH})\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	604 (619)	40.03 (38.45)	4.43 (4.52)	4	885	6.53	1.75	790
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{BrU}$								
$\text{UO}_2(5\text{-chlorosal-BZH})\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	575 (574.5)	41.21 (41.43)	4.91 (4.87)	4	905	6.80	1.74	810
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{ClU}$								
$\text{UO}_2(5\text{-nitrosal-BZH})\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	562 (585)	40.41 (40.69)	7.76 (7.18)	2	890	6.58	1.75	830
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_7\text{N}_2\text{U}$								
$\text{UO}_2(5\text{-methoxysal-BZH})\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	537 (570)	42.00 (41.75)	4.98 (4.91)	8	890	6.58	1.75	785
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{U}$								
$\text{UO}_2(3\text{-methoxysal-BZH})\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	557 (570)	41.46 (41.75)	4.58 (4.91)	8	895	6.65	1.74	790
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{U}$								
$\text{UO}_2(3\text{-ethoxysal-BZH})\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	576 (584)	41.03 (40.75)	4.99 (4.79)	6	905	6.80	1.74	800
$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{U}$								
$\text{UO}_2(3,5\text{-dichlorosal-BZH})\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	591 (609)	39.19 (39.08)	4.62 (4.59)	5	885	6.53	1.75	815
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{U}$								
$\text{UO}_2(\text{hydrox-BZH})\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	626 (590)	40.43 (40.34)	4.69 (4.74)	3	900	6.73	1.74	810
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{U}$								

(a) Abbreviations: BZH = benzoylhydrazide, sal = salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosal = 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosal = 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 5-methoxysal = 5-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 3-methoxysal = 3-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 3-ethoxysal = 3-ethoxysalicylaldehyde, 3,5-dichlorosal = 3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde, hydrox = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data indicate 1 : 1 metal : Schiff base stoichiometry and the complexes have the general formula $\text{UO}_2\text{L}\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (where LH_2 = tridentate dibasic Schiff base). The presence of methanol in the complexes has been confirmed from infrared spectral data. The complexes exhibit $\nu(\text{OH})$ stretch and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (CH_3OH) at $3300\text{-}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1000 cm^{-1} respectively^{8,9}. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ band of CH_3OH occurring at 1034 cm^{-1} undergoes a negative shift in the present complexes and this indicates the methanol coordination in the complexes^{9,10}. The complexes do not lose weight on heating at 120° for hours and this indicates that they retain CH_3OH at 120° and CH_3OH is coordinated to UO_2^{2+} . The molecular weight data indicate monomeric nature of the complexes. The complexes behave as non-electrolytes ($\Lambda_M = 2\text{-}8\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$) in methanol. The magnetic measurements indicate that the complexes are diamagnetic as expected for a $5f^0$ system. The complexes exhibit an electronic spectral band at $\sim 22000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the ${}^1E_g^+ \rightarrow {}^3\pi_u$ transition typical of OUO symmetric stretch frequency for the first excited state¹¹. The complexes are six-coordinate and octahedral.

The complexes exhibit a strong band at $885\text{-}910\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ ¹². The force constant (f) values (Table 1) for $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ agree well with the values reported in literature¹³. The $\text{U}-\text{O}$ bond length has been calculated with the help of the equation¹⁴: $R_{\text{U-O}} = 1.17 + 1.08 f^{-1/3}$. The $R_{\text{U-O}}$ in the complexes is in the range $1.72\text{-}1.75\text{ \AA}$ and the values are comparable to those ($1.60\text{-}1.92\text{ \AA}$) observed for other dioxouranium(VI) complexes¹⁵. The $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ stretch

occurs in the region $785\text{-}830\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Schiff bases exhibit a strong band in the region $1635\text{-}1670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretch. This band disappears in the complexes indicating the destruction of the carbonyl group due to enolisation and consequent coordination. Another strong band in the ligands at $1600\text{-}1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch and this band shifts to lower energy ($5\text{-}15\text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicating the participation of nitrogen atom in coordination¹⁷. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ phenolic stretch in the ligands is assigned in the region $1515\text{-}1565\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and this band shifts to higher energy by $5\text{-}25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating phenolic oxygen coordination of the Schiff bases¹⁸. Thus uranium(VI) is octahedrally coordinated to methanol, two oxygen atoms and the Schiff base.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for support.

References

1. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT, JR. and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 7, 83.
2. S. YAMADA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1963, 1, 415.
3. A. T. T. HSIEN, R. M. SHEAHAN and B. O. WEST, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, 28, 885.
4. L. GATTERMAN and H. WIELAND, "Laboratory Methods of Organic Chemistry", Macmillan, London, 1963, p. 153.
5. A. SYAMAL and K. S. KALE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16A, 46.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Third Edition, Longman, London, 1962, p. 539.
7. A. SYAMAL and O. P. SINGHAL, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal Org. Chem.*, 1980, 10, 243.
8. L. F. LINDOY and S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 2, 1149.

9. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1969, p. 220.
10. C. HERZBERG, "Molecular Spectra and Molecular Structure", D. Van Nostrand Co., New York, Vol. II, 1959, p. 335.
11. S. P. MCGLYNN and J. K. SMITH, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1961, **6**, 164.
12. M. M. JONES, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1955, **23**, 2105; A. E. COMYNS, B. M. GATEHOUSE and E. WATT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4655.
13. A. SYAMAL and O. P. SINGHAL, *Transition Metal Chem.*, 1979, **4**, 179.
14. S. P. MCGLYNN, J. K. SMITH and W. C. NEELV, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 105.
15. W. H. ZACHARIASEN, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1954, **8**, 847.
16. S. P. MCGLYNN, J. K. SMITH and W. C. NEELV, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 105.
17. J. E. COVACIC, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1967, **23A**, 183; F. MAGGIO, T. PIZZINO, V. ROMANO and G. DIA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 602.
18. S. J. GRUBBER, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1805.

Complexation of Chlorophenoxyacetic Acid Herbicides with Some Plant Metal Ions

R. SAHAI* and S. S. S. KUSHWAHA

Department of Chemistry, V. S. S. D. College, Kanpur-208 002

Manuscript received 28 October 1980, revised 2 May 1981,
accepted 15 July 1981

It has been observed in our previous investigation¹ that plant auxins, such as, indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), indole-3-propanoic acid (IPA), indole-3-butanoic acid (IBA) and naphthalene-1-acetic acid (NAA) form considerably stable complexes in solution with Mg(II), Al(III), Ca(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zr(IV), La(III) and Th(IV), thereby supporting complexation as the possible mode of action of these plant growth regulators. Since herbicide action is also an important process occurring in plants, the complexes of some herbicides, such as, PAA, 2, 4-D and 2, 4, 5-T with Al(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zr(IV) and Th(IV) have been studied in solution potentiometrically using Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique²⁻⁴, as employed by Irving and Rossotti⁵. The protonation constant of the ligands and the stepwise formation constants of these metal complexes have been calculated to explore complexation as a possible mode of action of these herbicides⁶⁻⁸.

Experimental

Material: All chemicals were of A. R. grade. The ligands were obtained direct from Fluka AG, Buchs, Switzerland and were used after further purification. Dioxan was purified by standard method and solutions of ligands were prepared in 50% aq. (v/v) dioxan and carbonate free double distilled water. Other solutions were prepared in water and standardised by appropriate standard

methods. A Beckman pH-meter having glass and calomel-electrode assembly was employed to record the pH values.

Procedure: The following three mixtures: (a) 10 ml (0.01 M) nitric acid + 5 ml (1.0 M) potassium nitrate, (b) mixture (a) + 10 ml (0.01 M) ligand solution, and (c) mixture (b) + 2 ml (0.01 M) metal solution, were prepared for each system (total volume 50 ml) and titrated against standard carbonate free 0.1 M NaOH solution at constant ionic strength 0.1 M (KNO₃) and temperature (20°) in 50% aq. dioxan(v/v). A 70% aq. dioxan(v/v) medium was chosen to keep the Zr(IV) and Th(IV) complexes in solution. The ratio of metal and ligand concentration was maintained 1:5 in order to satisfy the highest coordination number of the metal. From the pH-titration curves, values of various parameters (\bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL) were calculated by Irving Rossotti's methods⁵.

Results

Proton-Ligand systems: Ligand titration curves and the proton-ligand formation curves of the ligands under investigation clearly indicated the liberation of one proton showing the equilibrium, $HL \rightleftharpoons H^+ + L^-$. From proton-ligand formation curves, the values of protonation constants (pK_a) were obtained directly by interpolating at half \bar{n}_A values. The pK_a values of PAA, 2, 4-D and 2, 4, 5-T at 20° and 30° were found to be 4.58, 4.35, 4.20 and 4.32, 4.24, 4.08 respectively.

Metal-Ligand systems: Examination of the representative titration curves (Fig. 1) showed that

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves:

- A: Free acid (—●—●—●—);
 B: Free acid + 2,4-D (—Δ—Δ—Δ—);
 C: Cu(II)-2,4-D (—▷—▷—▷—);
 D: Al(III)-2,4-D (—□—□—□—);
 E: Zr(IV)-2,4-D (—○—○—○—).

* To whom all correspondence should be addressed.